

AeroCom Experiment: Dust Radiative Forcing from reconstructed dust changes since pre-industrial times (DURF)

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Deadlines for submission of model data: Tier I experiments: 31 March 2024; Tier II experiments: September 30, 2024.

Motivation:

A recent reconstruction of dust loading indicates that dust has increased by $55 \pm 30\%$ since pre-industrial times (Kok et al., 2023). This reconstruction was obtained by combining sedimentary records of dust deposition with observational and modeling constraints on the modern-day dust cycle from the DustCOMM data set (Kok et al., 2021a, b). In contrast, CMIP6 models with prognostic dust cycles simulate an approximately constant dust loading over the historical period (see figure), thus missing possibly important effects of increases in dust on the Earth's radiation budget and other components of the Earth system. We propose an experiment that uses the DustCOMM dust reconstruction to enable models to account for the historical dust increase and to calculate the resulting radiative perturbation due to dust interactions with radiation, clouds, and anthropogenic aerosols. This radiative perturbation is likely partly due to human land use changes (a forcing) and partly due to natural and anthropogenic climate changes (a feedback). Because these two contributions are difficult to disentangle, we refer to the entire radiative perturbation due to the historical change in dust as the dust effective radiative forcing.

Objectives:

- To quantify the direct radiative forcing (IRFari) due to the reconstructed increase in dust since pre-industrial times
- To quantify the effective radiative forcing (ERFaci) resulting from dust interactions with warm, mixed-phase, and cirrus clouds due to the reconstructed increase in dust since pre-industrial times
- To quantify the change in the radiative forcing of anthropogenic aerosols (ERFari and ERFaci) due to interactions with dust, for instance due to dust serving as a sink for anthropogenic aerosols and precursor gases.

Proposed model experiments:

Four atmosphere-only simulations of the period 1851 – 2000 (600 run years total) with prescribed SSTs at a minimum resolution of 2.5x2.5°. Simulations should otherwise follow the CMIP6 AerChemMIP histSST runs (see documentation provided [here](#)), including use of SSTs and sea ice from a coupled historical run or reanalysis, with the dust in these experiments differing as follows for four Tier I simulations:

Simulation name:	Dust emission fluxes:	Anthropogenic aerosols:	Purpose:
histSST	Prognostically calculated by model	Following CMIP6 emissions of aerosols and precursor gases	Base simulation
histSST-dust-glb	Prognostically calculated by model, but multiplied by an annually changing global tuning constant that forces a trend in global dust emissions that matches the DustCOMM reconstruction (file with tuning constants is here)	Following CMIP6 emissions of aerosols and precursor gases	Calculate radiative forcing due to global-scale historical increase in dust
histSST-dust-glb-piaer	Prognostically calculated by model, but multiplied by an annually changing global tuning constant that forces a trend in global dust emissions that matches the DustCOMM reconstruction (file with tuning constants is here)	Pre-industrial (1850) aerosols and precursor gases.	Diagnose effect of interactions between increasing anthropogenic aerosols and increasing dust so we can separate their effects
histSST-dust-spt	2D monthly bulk dust fluxes are read in from emissions files that will be provided based on the DustCOMM dust reconstruction (directory with annual emission files is here)	Following CMIP6 emissions of aerosols and precursor gases	Calculate radiative forcing due to historical increase in dust, with regional resolution in changes in dust emission fluxes

Because of intermodel differences in the assumed size distribution at emission and the dust lifetime, the DustCOMM emissions could lead to a wide range of global dust optical depth values, including values that are far outside of observational constraints. Therefore, all Tier I simulations that use DustCOMM emissions (histSST-dust-glb, histSST-dust-glb-piaer, and histSST-dust-spt) should tune such that the

global dust AOD in the last decade (1991 – 2000) is consistent with the constraints on the global dust AOD of 0.030 ± 0.010 (95% confidence interval) obtained by Ridley et al. (2016) and largely confirmed by subsequent work (Voss and Evan 2020, Gkikas et al. 2021). The simplest way to do so is to add a global tuning constant when applying the DustCOMM emissions that brings the global DAOD within the 0.030 ± 0.010 range. Another way to achieve this for some models, especially for those that have too much fine dust and not enough coarse dust in comparison with observational constraints (Ryder et al. 2019, Adebisi and Kok 2020), could be to adjust the emitted dust size distribution to be consistent with observational constraints, such as in (Meng et al. 2022).

All Tier I simulations should output the fields listed below. All simulations should make two separate radiation calls to enable the quantification of dust direct radiative forcing: once with no aerosols and once with dust and anthropogenic aerosols (both listed below).

In addition, participating models are encouraged to provide the following 5-year long, nudged Tier II simulations to investigate dust radiative forcing in more detail, following the approach in McGraw et al. (2020; see their Equation 1) to disentangle the various radiative effects of dust. These simulations should follow the setup for the histSST-dust-spt simulation, with the following modifications; wind fields should be nudged to 2000-2004 (as in EMISSION-MIP, [here](#)) and anthropogenic aerosols emission should be set to 2000-2004. Changes from that simulation should be applied as listed in the table below:

Simulation name:	Model changes:	Purpose:
dust-ctrl	<p>Perform 5-year atmosphere-only run following histSST-dust-spt with prescribed dust emissions from 1996-2000 but nudged to 2000-2004 winds (as in EMISSION-MIP)</p> <p>Encouraged optional diagnostics: SW and LW radiation calls with each individual particle bin or mode removed for radiation at surface and TOA and for all-sky and clear-sky conditions. Output additional monthly fields of direct radiative effect per particle bin or mode (from subtracting radiation call with aerosols from that with each individual bin or mode removed) for SW and LW, TOA and surface, clear-sky and all-sky. Also output additional monthly fields per particle bin or mode for dust AOD, dust absorption AOD, dust column load, dust emission rate, dust dry and</p>	<p>Base simulation for other Tier 2 experiments.</p> <p>The optional diagnostics will be used to understand the role of the dust size distribution on the dust radiative effect and the simulated global dust cycle, and to bias correct models using observational constraints on dust size distributions.</p>

	wet deposition flux, and dust surface concentration.	
dust-ctrl_PI	As dust-ctrl, but with pre-industrial dust emissions (1851 - 1855)	PI version of base simulation duster-ctrl. The difference between dust-ctrl and dust-ctrl_PI gives the anthropogenic dust radiative effect (for this setup) with all direct and indirect effect active
dust-ctrl-swnormal dust-ctrl-swlessabs dust-ctrl-swmoreabs	<p>Perform 3 different 5-year runs with dust SW optics based on experimental constraints on the wavelength-dependent imaginary index of refraction in Table 4 of Di Biagio et al. (2019):</p> <p>(1) average: use the “median” values (0.0026 at 370 nm, decreasing to 0.0009 at 950 nm)</p> <p>(2) less absorbing: use the “10 %” values (0.0012 at 370 nm, decreasing to 0.0004 at 950 nm)</p> <p>(3) more absorbing dust: use the “90%” values (0.0061 at 370 nm, decreasing to 0.0015 at 950 nm).</p> <p>The real refractive index should be the same for all three runs and ideally should be set to the “median” value of 1.52 obtained in Table 4 of Di Biagio et al. (2019).</p> <p>Encouraged optional diagnostics: SW and LW radiation calls with each individual particle bin or mode removed for radiation at surface and TOA and for all-sky and clear-sky conditions. Output additional monthly fields of direct radiative effect per particle bin or mode (from subtracting radiation call with aerosols from that with each individual bin or mode removed) for SW and LW, TOA and surface, clear-sky and all-sky.</p>	The optional diagnostics will be used to understand the role of dust optical properties on the dust radiative effect and semi-direct cloud effects.

no-dust-DirectEff	As dust-ctrl but with scattering and absorption by dust turned off.	To diagnose dust semi-direct effects, following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
no-dust-DirectEff-PI	As no-dust-DirectEff, but with PI (1851-1855) dust emissions	To diagnose dust semi-direct effects, following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
no-dust-INPs	For models that use a dust-dependent INP parameterization: as no-Dust-DirectEff, but using an aerosol-independent INP parameterization.	To diagnose dust indirect effects on mixed-phase clouds, , following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
no-dust_INPs-PI	As no-dust-INPs, but with PI (1851-1855) dust emissions	To diagnose dust indirect effects in mixed-phase clouds, , following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
no-dust-in-cirrus	For models that use a dust-dependent INP parameterization; as no-dust_INPs-PI, but with ice nucleation on dust in cirrus clouds turned off.	To diagnose dust indirect effects in cirrus clouds, following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
no-dust-in-cirrus-PI	As no-dust-in-cirrus, but with PI (1851-1855) dust emissions	To diagnose dust indirect effects in cirrus clouds, following McGraw et al. (2020, Equation 1)
anthr_aero_PI	As dust-ctrl, but with PI (1850) anthropogenic aerosol emission	To diagnose dust impacts on anthropogenic aerosols and the resulting modulation of the anthropogenic aerosol direct effect and indirect cloud effects

The total number of model simulation years for all Tier II experiments combined is 60 years.

Model output:

Your AeroCom file name (one variable per file) should look like this:

aerocom3_⟨ModelName⟩_DURF-⟨SimulationName⟩_⟨VariableName⟩_⟨VerticalCoordinateType⟩_⟨Year⟩_monthly.nc

Examples:

2-D: aerocom3_GEOS-i33p2_DURF-histSST_ps_Surface_2008_monthly.nc

3-D: aerocom3_GEOS-i33p2_DURF-histSST-dust-sp__rho_ModelLevel_2009_monthly.nc

Where the <VariableName> is in lower case, and the <VerticalCoordinateType> for each set of variables is varying and listed in the tables below (Mixed with Upper and lower cases).

Please submit as many of the variables listed below as possible (not all models will have all variables). These are “priority 1” variables listed in the AeroCom III Excel sheet. You can refer to AeroCom III-DURF output specifications for detailed information and requirements there (the required diagnostic fields are listed under column “DURF”). The variable below also include fields with radiative effects without dust. These are helpful for us to have, but optional. In other words, please output these if your model already calculates these but it's not a problem if your model does not output these. You are also encouraged to submit the “priority 2” variables if they are available.

In addition to the fields below, please also provide the dust bin size limits (for sectional models) or mode lognormal parameters (for modal models) as well as the optical properties (MEE, SSA, and asymmetry factor) for each particle bin or mode (for pure dust at emission, if the optical properties change during transport).

2-D fixed variables:

Variable	Variable name ⁺	Variable unit ⁺	Also needed if not participating in Tier 2?
Surface altitude (relative to sea level)	orog	m	Yes
Area of each grid box	areacella	m ²	Yes
Land area fraction	sftlf	1	Yes

⁺Name required by AEROCOM III

2-D variables:

Variable	Variable name ⁺	Variable unit ⁺	Temporal frequency	Also needed if not participating in Tier 2?
<i>Met. fields:</i>	VerticalCoordinateType: Surface			
Surface air pressure	ps	Pa	Monthly	Yes
Tropopause air pressure	ptp	Pa	Monthly	Yes
Soil moisture of top soil layer	mrsos	kg/kg or m ³ /m ³	Monthly	Yes

Leaf area index	lai	m ² /m ²	Monthly	Yes
Friction velocity	ustar	m s ⁻¹	Monthly	Yes
Tropopause altitude	ztp	m	Monthly	Yes
Tropopause air temperature	tatp	K	Monthly	Yes
Sea surface temperature	tos	K	Monthly	Yes
Surface temperature	ts	K	Monthly	Yes
Near-surface air temperature	tas	K	Monthly	Yes
Precipitation	pr	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Monthly	Yes
Snowfall flux	prsn	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Monthly	Yes
Convective precipitation	prc	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Monthly	Yes
Atmospheric boundary layer depth	bldep	m	Monthly	Yes
Convective cloud area fraction	convclt	1	Monthly	No
Ice water path	clivi	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Liquid water path	lwp	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Total cloud fraction	clt	1	Monthly	Yes
Low cloud fraction	cldlow	1	Monthly	No
Medium cloud fraction	cldmed	1	Monthly	No
High cloud fraction	cldhgh	1	Monthly	No
<i>Radiation fields:</i>	VerticalCoordinateType: Surface			
TOA outgoing shortwave radiation	rsut	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes

TOA incident shortwave radiation	rsdt	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing clear-sky shortwave radiation	rsutcs	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing longwave radiation	rlut	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing clear-sky longwave radiation	rlutcs	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
surface downwelling shortwave radiation	rsds	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling shortwave radiation	rsus	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
surface downwelling longwave radiation	rlds	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling longwave radiation	rlus	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsutca	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing clear-sky shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsutcsca	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing longwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rlutca	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
TOA outgoing clear-sky longwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rlutcsca	W m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes

surface downwelling shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsdsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface downwelling clear-sky shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsdscsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsusca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling clear-sky shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rsuscscsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface downwelling longwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rldsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface downwelling clear-sky longwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rldscsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling shortwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rlusca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling clear-sky longwave radiation without aerosol radiative effect	rluscscsca	W m-2	Monthly	Yes
surface upwelling clear-sky longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rluscscd	W m-2	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)

TOA outgoing shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsuted	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
TOA outgoing clear-sky shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsutcsed	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
TOA outgoing longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rlutcd	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
TOA outgoing clear-sky longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rlutcsed	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface downwelling shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsdscd	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface downwelling clear-sky shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsdscsed	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface upwelling shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsusc	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface upwelling clear-sky shortwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rsuscscd	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface downwelling longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rldscd	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
surface downwelling clear-sky longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rldscsed	W m ⁻²	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)

surface upwelling longwave radiation without dust radiative effect	rlused	W m-2	Monthly	If possible (see comment above)
<i>Encouraged for Tier II simulations: radiation fields per bin or mode:</i>	VerticalCoordinateType: Surface			
TOA shortwave clear-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudrestcsb1, dudrestcsb2, ..., dudrestcsbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
TOA shortwave all-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudrestasb1, dudrestasb2, ..., dudrestasbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
TOA longwave clear-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudreltcsb1, dudreltcsb2, ..., dudreltcsbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
TOA longwave all-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudreltasb1, dudreltasb2, ..., dudreltasbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
Surface shortwave clear-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudresscsb1, dudresscsb2, ..., dudresscsbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
Surface shortwave all-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudressasb1, dudressasb2, ..., dudressasbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
Surface longwave clear-sky radiative effect for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)	dudrelscsb1, dudrelscsb2, ..., dudrelscsbx	W m-2	Monthly	No
Surface longwave all-sky radiative effect	dudrelsasb1, dudrelsasb2, ..., dudrelsasbx	W m-2	Monthly	No

for each dust bin or mode (1,2,...,x)				
Dust aerosol optical thickness at 550 nm per bin or mode	od550dustb1, od550dustb2, ..., od550dustbx	1	Monthly	No
Dust aerosol absorption optical thickness at 550 nm per bin or mode	abs550dustb1, abs550dustb2, ..., abs550dustbx	1	Monthly	No
Column dust mass load per bin or mode	loaddub1, loaddub2, ..., loaddubx	kg m-2	Monthly	No
Dust emission rate per bin or mode	emidustb1, emidustb2, ..., emidustbx	kg m-2 s-1	Monthly	No
Dust dry deposition flux per bin or mode	drydustb1, drydustb2, ..., drydustbx	kg m-2 s-1	Monthly	No
Dust wet deposition flux per bin or mode	wetdustb1, wetdustb2, ..., wetdustbx	kg m-2 s-1	Monthly	No
Dust surface concentration per bin or mode	sconcdustb1, sconcdustb2, ..., sconcdustbx	kg m-3	Monthly	No
<i>Emission, deposition, surface concentration, load for dust:</i>				
Total Emission Rate of Dust	emidust	kg m-2 s-1	Monthly	Yes
Dry deposition rate of dust (should be sum of dry turbulent and sedimentation deposition fluxes)	drydust	kg m-2 s-1	Monthly	Yes

Wet deposition rate of dust	wetdust	kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Monthly	Yes
Surface concentration of dust	sconcdust	kg m ⁻³	Monthly	Yes
Column dust mass load	loaddu	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column PM1 dust mass load	loadlt1d	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column PM2.5 dust mass load	loadlt25d	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column PM10 dust mass load	loadlt10du	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
<i>Load for other aerosol species:</i>				
Column black carbon mass load	loadbc	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column organic aerosol mass load	loadoa	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column secondary organic aerosol mass load	loadsoa	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column sea-salt mass load	loadss	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column sulfate mass load	loadso4	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column nitrate mass load	loadno3	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column methanesulfonic acid mass load	loadmsa	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column sulfur dioxide mass load	loadso2	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes
Column dimethyl sulfide mass load	loaddms	kg m ⁻²	Monthly	Yes

Column ammonium mass load	Loadnh4	kg m-2	Monthly	Yes
Column ammonia mass load	loadnh3	kg m-2	Monthly	Yes
Column nitric acid mass load	loadhno3	kg m-2	Monthly	Yes
<i>Optical depth:</i>				
Cloud optical depth	dtau	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient aerosol optical thickness at 550 nm	od550aer	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient aerosol optical thickness at 550 nm in clear sky	od550csaer	1	Monthly	Yes
sulfate aod@550nm	od550so4	1	Monthly	Yes
black carbon aod@550nm	od550bc	1	Monthly	Yes
Organic matter aod@550nm	od550oa	1	Monthly	Yes
SOA aod@550nm	od550soa	1	Monthly	Yes
Nitrate aod@550nm	od550no3	1	Monthly	Yes
Sea salt aod@550nm	od550ss	1	Monthly	Yes
Dust aod@550nm	od550dust	1	Monthly	Yes
Dust aod@1000nm	od1000dust	1	Monthly	No
Dust aod@10um	od10umdust	1	Monthly	Yes
PM1 dust aod@550nm	od550lt1du	1	Monthly	Yes
PM2p5 dust aod@550nm	od550lt2p5du	1	Monthly	Yes

PM10 dust aod@550nm	od550lt10du	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient aerosol absorption optical thickness at 550 nm	abs550aer	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient BC absorption optical thickness at 550 nm	abs550bc	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient OC absorption optical thickness at 550 nm	abs550oc	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient dust absorption optical thickness at 550 nm	abs550dust	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient dust absorption optical thickness at 440 nm	abs440dust	1	Monthly	Yes
ambient dust absorption optical thickness at 870 nm	abs870dust	1	Monthly	Yes

3-D variables:

Variable	Variable name ⁺	Variable unit ⁺	Temporal frequency	Also needed if not participating in Tier 2?
<i>Met. fields:</i>	<i>VerticalCoordinateType: ModelLevel</i>			
air pressure	pfull	Pa	Monthly	Yes
air pressure at interfaces	phalf	Pa	Monthly	Yes
air temperature	Ta	K	Monthly	Yes
Specific humidity	hus	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes

Eastward wind	ua	m s-1	Monthly	Yes
Northward wind	va	m s-1	Monthly	Yes
Upward air velocity	wa	m s-1	Monthly	No
Shortwave heating rate	tntrs	K s-1	Monthly	Yes
Longwave heating rate	tntrl	K s-1	Monthly	Yes
Air density	rho	kg m-3	Monthly	Yes
Layer thickness	dh	m	Monthly	Yes
Cloud area fraction	clt	1	Monthly	Yes
Convective cloud area fraction	convclt	1	Monthly	No
Cloud condensation nuclei concentration at 0.5% supersaturation	ccn	m-3	Monthly	Yes
Mass fraction of cloud liquid water	clw	kg kg-1	Monthly	No
Mass fraction of cloud ice water	cli	kg kg-1	Monthly	No
Droplet number concentration (grid box mean)	cdnc	m-3	Monthly	No
Ice crystal number concentration (grid box mean)	inc	m-3	Monthly	No
Cloud frequency of occurrence (1 if cloud is present, 0 if not)		1	Monthly	No
<i>Extinction:</i>	<i>VerticalCoordinateType: ModelLevel</i>			
Aerosol extinction @ 550nm	ec550aer	m-1	Monthly	Yes

Dust extinction @ 550 nm	ec550dust	m-1	Monthly	Yes
Dust extinction @ 10 um	ec10umdust	m-1	Monthly	Yes
<i>Mixing ratio and production rate:</i>	<i>VerticalCoordinateType: ModelLevel</i>			
PM2.5 mass mixing ratio	mmrpm2p5	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes
PM10 mass mixing ratio	mmrpm10	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes
PM1 mass mixing ratio	mmrpm1	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes
dust mass mixing ratio	mmrdust	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes
Aerosol water mass mixing ratio	mmraerh2o	kg kg-1	Monthly	Yes

Model output submission:

Please refer to the AeroCom website: https://aerocom.met.no/FAQ/data_access/submit_data.

References:

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